

CHALLENGES IN FORMING EFFECTIVE LEGAL FRAMEWORKS TO COUNTERACT MASS DISORDERS

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ABSTRACT: This article examines the challenges involved in forming effective legal frameworks to counteract mass disorders, focusing on the improvement of criminal and administrative legislation aimed at protecting public order and public security. The study analyzes the legal nature of mass disorders, the grounds for legal liability, and the adequacy of existing normative regulations in addressing contemporary threats to social stability.

Particular attention is paid to the coherence of criminal law norms, the proportionality of sanctions, and the differentiation of liability for organizers, instigators, and active participants in mass disorders. The article also explores preventive legal mechanisms, including early warning measures, administrative supervision, and interagency coordination among law enforcement bodies. Based on a comparative legal analysis and doctrinal approaches, the study identifies legislative gaps and proposes recommendations for enhancing the effectiveness of legal regulation and preventive policies in this field.

Keywords: mass disorders; public order; public security; legal frameworks; criminal liability; administrative liability; crime prevention; law enforcement agencies; legislative improvement.

Mass riots pose a real threat to public safety, public order, the foundations of the constitutional system, and state security. This necessitates timely theoretical, scientific, and practical research aimed at preventing them. Such research provides the basis for the urgent adoption of appropriate measures to protect life, health, and

property, and to restore the normal functioning of infrastructure and essential facilities.

Mass riots are a broad phenomenon encompassing a combination of various socially dangerous actions, primarily violent ones, committed primarily by large groups, threatening the foundations of public safety and capable of destabilizing the activities of government bodies, institutions, and other organizations, as well as significantly disrupting public order in key areas. The high level of social danger and the widespread scale of mass riots require the development and continuous improvement of measures to combat these criminal incidents, particularly preventative ones, taking into account the modern criminal law and criminological characteristics of such criminal aggression.

The prevention of mass unrest in modern conditions is further complicated by the fact that their organization, support of such unrest and its direct implementation are often associated with the criminal activities of extremist and terrorist associations and organizations, primarily with the dissemination of the corresponding ideology and the active use for this purpose of the broad capabilities of the Internet and other information and communication technologies [1].

According to ACLED, a non-governmental organization that collects, analyzes, and maps crises, and Princeton University's BDI research group, there were 1,040 riots of varying sizes in the United States from January 2020 to March 2022, resulting in at least 26 deaths [2].

The criminalization of mass riots can be based on distinguishing the following criminal-legal and criminological characteristics of mass riots: their violent nature; the heterogeneity of the individuals involved; extremist orientation and motivation; "mass character," expressed in significant quantitative indicators of riot participants; the potential to become a means of implementing "color revolutions"; and the potential for transformation into a type of political crime.

American federal criminal law does not provide for a distinction in the criminal liability of the perpetrator of a crime (public riots) depending on their functions as organizer, witness, assistant, or perpetrator (direct participant). Taking into account the specifics of the formation of the material element of mass riots in § 231 U.S. Code (Civil Disorders) and the main components of mass riots in § 2101 U.S. Code (Riots), a comparative legal analysis was conducted (in the synchronous section), which found that in the first case, mass riots are not considered a crime, and criminal liability is provided for actions that contribute to mass riots and increase their social danger: a) assistance in training future participants in mass riots in the skills of handling weapons, explosives and incendiary devices; b) transportation or preparation for transportation of the said means of crime and weapons for subsequent illegal use for the purpose of ensuring mass riots; and c) actions aimed at obstructing, disrupting or negatively affecting the work of firefighters or law enforcement officers lawfully performing their duties during civil unrest [3].

Mass riots pose a social danger because they disrupt the functioning of government bodies, spread widely throughout public order, threaten public safety, result in human casualties, and cause serious economic damage to the state (society, and individuals). Analysis of mass riots shows that this dangerous crime undermines the foundations of society, disrupts stability, disrupts the normal life of citizens, and disrupts the operation of businesses, institutions, and organizations.

Criminal actions by large crowds are typically accompanied by aggression, intense interpersonal interaction, and the arousal of passions.

As is well known, accurate information about the participants in mass riots, the scale of their illegal actions, and their material consequences is not always available, which partially limits the ability to combat this crime. Given the above, mass riots can be understood as mass actions expressed in various forms of violence, posing a real threat to society and the personal safety of citizens.

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A rally is a gathering held to discuss important events, political, or socioeconomic issues. A rally is usually understood as a gathering of a specific political group, mass movement, or industrial organization in a state of unrest or dissatisfaction with the actions of government authorities, in city centers to express their views and demands [4].

In preventing mass unrest, it is also important to reduce the negative (destructive) impact of the media and various internet resources on the population, especially young people. This primarily involves monitoring the information published (posted) in these resources to identify extremist and other prohibited content and subsequently blocking the relevant resource. It is also important to exercise caution when preparing and publishing (posting) information about crimes allegedly committed by individuals or representatives of foreign authorities, about the methods and means used to commit various crimes, about whether participants in certain illegal mass protests received monetary compensation from their organizers, etc.

It is important to develop cultural and moral measures aimed at developing knowledge, skills, and competencies in adolescents and young adults about the specifics of state policy, the behavioral culture associated with fan support for a sports team, the culture of expressing political and other grievances, as well as legally and morally acceptable methods for resolving various social conflicts. Based

on the above considerations, it can be said that a systemic approach is necessary to prevent mass unrest and establish appropriate criminal penalties. This work can only yield positive results if civil society institutions actively and consistently participate in preventing mass unrest.

K.R. Abdurasulova, emphasizing that the terms "crime prevention" and "crime prevention" cannot be given different meanings, as they are used in the same sense in general political, legal, and philological literature, and that there is no distinction between the terms as defined in legislation, provides the following definition: "Crime prevention or crime prevention is the activity of state bodies (including law enforcement agencies), public associations, organizations, institutions, and citizens aimed at neutralizing or eliminating the conditions and causes that create opportunities for the commission of crimes, encompassing various measures (influence measures) and targeting objective external factors and specific individuals" [5]. Scholars have various conflicting approaches to the concept of "prevention." Some scholars consider the concept of "prevention" to be applicable only to crime prevention, while others consider it applicable to all areas.

Prevention should be understood as an activity aimed, firstly, at identifying the causes and conditions that make the commission of a crime possible, and, secondly, at identifying the person who may commit the crime (taking advantage of its antisocial nature) and taking the necessary preventive measures against them.

At the same time, a number of dictionaries also consider the term "prevention" to mean "prevention." In the explanatory dictionary of the Uzbek language, the concept of "prevention" is explained in Greek as "prophylacticos", meaning "protector", "preventive", and is defined as "measures taken to prevent premature failure, breakdown of an event, mechanism, machine".

From this perspective, it is appropriate to adapt the provisions of Uzbekistan's criminal legislation on liability for mass riots.

High-tech means and weapons of crime are material objects, qualitatively different technological processes, and methods used by the perpetrator of a crime to organize mass riots, provoke mass riots, incite and attract others to mass riots, or directly participate in such riots (information and communication technologies such as social media, instant messaging apps, etc.; mobile and satellite communications; unmanned aerial vehicles; 3D printing technologies and the means of physical destruction created using them). Therefore, it is important to correctly and accurately characterize the criminal weapons used in mass riots.

To effectively combat this crime, it is proposed to develop a draft concept for "Mass Riots". Based on projected approaches and methods for preventing mass riots, it defines the goals, objectives, principles, key activities, and mechanisms of state policy in the area of preventing mass riots, which should include the possibility of using high-tech means and tools. The complex socioeconomic and political situation in the country and the fragmentation of ideological ties have led to the emergence of tensions and conflicts in society based on differences in economic, national, religious, political, and other interests. The current situation clearly impacts the fight against crime in general and its specific forms, and to a certain extent, this also applies to mass unrest. The turbulent global situation can influence the changes occurring in our society, and there is a risk of mass events, including various rallies, marches, demonstrations, etc. In such conditions, mass events with negative connotations, which undermine public order and public safety, are also widespread. Therefore, it is entirely reasonable to conclude that, given the growing development of society, an increase in crimes such as mass unrest should be expected in some regions.

To thoroughly study any event or process, it is necessary, first and foremost, to conduct a comprehensive study of its characteristics, features, and mechanisms.

Mass riots can also be understood through a full analysis of their nature. It is advisable to begin the analysis with an examination of the classification of mass riots.

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The main criteria for classifying mass riots are the characteristics and consequences of their occurrence.

Criminal actions during mass riots are divided into two types: general and specific. General characteristics of mass riots include vandalism aimed at the destruction of institutions, stores, vehicles, arson, and other similar acts. Specific mass riots involve the invasion of citizens' homes.

When organizing efforts to prevent mass unrest, it is necessary to consider that conflicts in the social environment play a significant role in their occurrence, and therefore, it is necessary to coordinate the activities of state and public institutions, organizations, and enterprises. It is advisable to take steps to create specialized legislation that would standardize the activities of law enforcement agencies in fulfilling these tasks.

Based on the above considerations, it should be noted that strengthening the content, characteristics, and liability for mass riots in legislation, clearly defining the forms of mass riots, and improving measures to prevent and combat mass riots, especially given the dangers arising in cyberspace, are important tasks facing criminal law and practice.

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